

2. Linear decrease in water applied and corresponding crop response, i.e. dry weight of tops and visual drought score after 47 and 61 days.

Although space restrictions prohibit the illustration of all the variables measured, we found a high correlation of such responses as dry matter accumulation, leaf area index, plant height, leaf water potential, drought resistance score, yield, and yield components with the water applied. That finding illustrates the technique's usefulness in research where water is a primary variable. The line source sprinkler may be used at a particular growth stage such as the very sensitive flowering stage. We plan to use it to develop a drought screening method that will be sensitive to yield and percentage sterility.

The line source sprinkler technique was developed by Dr. R. J. Hanks and

associates at Utah State University, USA. It should be particularly useful in climates where a distinct dry season allows its use without rainfall. If properly used, the technique would shorten to one or two dry seasons the

many years of multilocal testing, which are costly and involve the problem of interpreting the complex effects of natural droughts. Interested rice scientists may contact the authors for further details. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Adverse soils tolerance

Zinc deficiency – a new problem for irrigated rice in Bangladesh

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The introduction of modern rice varieties has intensified rice cultivation in Bangladesh, particularly in areas with dry-season irrigation. Newer BRRI varieties adapted to various locations and seasons have changed the total cropping patterns substantially in irrigated rice lands. Additional irrigation facilities and projects have further intensified rice production. But the intensive wetland rice cultivation has also brought about new soil problems.

Because of several field reports on the poor performance of the modern varieties in some irrigated areas of Bangladesh, we conducted a preliminary survey to

identify the actual field problems of rice cultivation in major rice-growing areas of Bangladesh in the 1978–79 aus, aman, and boro seasons. In some irrigated lands, particularly in the alkaline zone, we observed a new nutritional problem associated with continuous wetland conditions.

In large areas of alkaline soils in the Ganges-Kobadak Project in north-western Bangladesh with year-round irrigation, rice plants were characterized by stunted growth, poor root development, and in severe cases, rusty brown spots on the leaves. Similar symptoms were also observed in Faridpur, Kishoreganj, Chittagong, Barisal, Comilla, and Dacca districts. Suspecting zinc deficiency, we collected soil and plant samples for laboratory analysis. The results confirmed our field observations (see table).

Soil and plant analyses data on some selected samples with suspected zinc deficiency. Bangladesh Rice Research Institute.

Location	District	pH	Soil characteristics		Plant zinc (ppm)	Variety
			Organic matter (%)	0.05N HCl ^a extractable zinc (ppm)		
DND project	Dacca	7.40	n.a.	0.48	21.1	IR8
CIP	Comilla	7.40	1.72	0.52	12.5	IR8
Gournadi	Barisal	6.85	2.29	0.83	n.a.	local
BRRI station	Rajshahi	8.00	1.05	0.00	18.6	IRTN line
Kanaipur	Faridpur	7.70	1.76	0.08	n.a.	IR8
Mohanandapur	Faridpur	7.80	1.64	0.07	12.5	IR8
Kaijuri	Faridpur	7.90	2.07	0.10	14.5	IR8
Sajekupa	Jessore	7.40	2.10	0.28	15.7	IR8, BR1
Amla	Kushtia	7.40	2.48	0.13	9.6	BR3, BR1
Sandwip	Chittagong	7.95	1.50	0.95	19.6	IR8
Jhenaida	Jessore	7.78	2.27	0.14	28.0	IR8, BR3
Maria	Kishoreganj	6.90	2.00	2.08	18.8	IR8
Gangail	Kishoreganj	7.20	1.81	2.48	19.7	BR3, IR8
Santhia	Pabna	7.85	2.25	0.10	20.1	BR4
BAU	Mymensingh	7.40	1.98	1.46	15.9	IR8

^aExtractable soil zinc was estimated by the Katyal and Ponnampuruma method. n.a. = not analyzed.

Application of zinc salts effectively minimized the problem at some locations where it was severe. We suspect that zinc deficiency threatens higher yields in intensive rice cropping areas with alkaline and saline soils.

The cheapest way to handle the problem where available soil zinc is above the critical level is to dry the soil between two rice crops. In soils with low zinc, zinc sulfate or zinc oxide should be applied along with the normally applied fertilizers. Such requirement would mean additional input costs for many Bangladesh farmers. ■

Coastal saline soils in the Philippines as potential rice lands

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To ascertain the potential of Philippine coastal saline soils as rice lands, the performance of a total of 26 salt-tolerant rices was studied in 24 replicated experiments at 14 sites in farmers' fields from 1977 to 1979. The soils at the sites were characterized chemically and hydrologically, and the salt dynamics was monitored. The plants were scored visually for salt injury.

The soils ranged from 4.4 to 7.8 in pH, from 1.3 to 15.4% in organic matter content, and from moderate to high in nutrient status. Of the high-pH soils, seven were zinc deficient and two were boron toxic. The two strongly acid soils were iron toxic. Intrusion of seawater, saline creek water, or saline groundwater affected all 14 sites, especially in the dry season; deep flooding in the wet season occurred at 4 sites. The salt concentration increased during the dry season and decreased in the wet. EC values ranged from 1 to 15 mmho/cm during the year.

The performance of the rices varied with salt concentration, water availability in the dry season, and flood damage in the wet season. On slightly saline soils not subject to drought or deep flooding, the salt-tolerant pest-resistant semidwarf's

IR42, IR2071-105-4, IR2307-247-2, IR4619-48-3, IR4630-22-2, IR9884-3-3, and IR9884-54-3 yielded more than 4 t/ha.

There is promise that yields on current

saline rice fields can be increased and that coastal soils where salinity and flooding are not severe can be made into productive rice lands without costly inputs. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Deep water

Design of a deepwater tank for ufra research

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In previous varietal screening in Bangladesh against ufra disease of deepwater rice (caused by stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* Filipjev), leaf sheaths were inoculated with nematodes to achieve adequate infestation. This procedure may not be appropriate because it does not help detect sources of resistance on the basis of difference in the surface properties of the rice plant, e.g. how smooth or how tightly wrapped the leaf sheaths are. These properties could be particularly important under natural conditions

because they enable the nematodes to move from the water, through which they spread and reach the young tissues on which they feed. Therefore a special deepwater tank (see figure) was constructed at BRRI to simulate natural infestation under controlled conditions on a large scale.

The main experimental tank (20- X 20-m area, 2 m deep), whose walls are made of earth, is supplied with water from a tubewell. The water level can be maintained at 0.5 m, in spite of irregular rainfall, by inserting a constant level device in the drain conduit. It is important that water leaving the tank complex contain no live nematodes that might infest farmers' fields or nearby experimental sites. The water is led through a series of sedimentation chambers arranged in a row along one wall of the tank. The concrete-lined

A deepwater tank for ufra research, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute. (Note the sedimentation chambers along the far wall of the tank, and the use of polythene cages and miniature deepwater tanks to partition the main tank.)